

THE SOCIO-DYNAMIC DEVELOPMENT OF AVIATION
TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN**Rano Ergashova Turayevna**Professor, Military Aviation Institute,
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20093833>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 03rd May 2026Accepted: 05th May 2026Online: 07th May 2026**KEYWORDS***aviation terminology, socio-dynamics, sociolinguistics, terminological system, variation, borrowing, semantic expansion, comparative analysis, standardization***ABSTRACT**

This article examines the socio-dynamics of aviation terminology in English and Russian, analyzing the processes of its formation, development, and use within the framework of sociolinguistic factors influencing these processes. Particular attention is given to the interrelation between aviation terminology and the social environment, including the impact of professional communities, international standardization processes, and technological advancement on terminological change.

The formation and development of aviation terms are directly related to the socio-ethical characteristics of the society and professional groups that use them. The socially variable nature of language is explained primarily by U. Labov's theory of variation¹. According to him, language units differ in terms of professional roles within society, level of experience, communication conditions, and level of education². Aviation terms also exhibit such variability: for example, in English, units such as rotate, flare, crosswind component are used in a strictly technical sense in the speech of experienced pilots, while their semantic expansion or narrowing is observed among new pilots or multinational crews. In the experience of Russian aviation, the different use of terms such as *отказ, тяга, глиссада* between military and civil aviation is a clear manifestation of the social differential variability described by Labov.

In explaining the cognitive and social properties of aviation terms, the theory of linguistic relativism of E. Sapir and Whorf also provides an important scientific basis. According to it, language determines the way people perceive the world, which is also reflected in the aviation field, since aviation language forms the professional thinking system of a specialist³. Terms such as stall, clearance, altitude in English determine the model of situational perception of the global aviation community. Units such as *эшелон, подкрылок,*

¹ Labov W. *Sociolinguistic Patterns*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press. 1972. – P. 234.

² Labov W. *The Social Stratification of English in New York City*. Washington, DC: Center for Applied Linguistics. 1966. – P. 212.

³ Sapir E. *Language: An Introduction to the Study of Speech*. New York: Harcourt, Brace. 1921 – P. 135; Whorf B.L. *Language, Thought, and Reality: Selected Writings*. Edited by J. B. Carroll. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. 1956 – P. 176.

боковой ветер, characteristic of Russian aviation terminology, reflect the uniqueness of the Russian technical conceptual space.

Trudgill's sociolinguistic social network theory plays an important role in explaining the social formation of language and the subvariants that arise in professional groups⁴. Trudgill emphasizes the formation of language by social networks, communities and professional groups⁵. In the aviation sector, this is reflected in the regional microvariants of aviation English: differences in the use of terms such as taxiway, hold short, rollout in aviation schools in the USA, Great Britain and Australia fully confirm Trudgill's theory. In Russian aviation, semantic differentiation of terms is observed between the Moscow central dispatch network, regional airports and military aviation.

The sociolinguistic dynamics of aviation terms are also closely related to state policy and international norms, which is scientifically substantiated by B. Spolsky's theory of language policy. The linguist emphasizes that the choice and standardization of language is determined by institutional policy⁶. The strict standardization of English aviation terms by ICAO - the use of mandatory units such as Mayday, Pan Pan, Readback - is a clear example of institutional regulation. In the Russian aviation language, the formation of terms is regulated by national aviation standards, which indicates that the language changes in connection with state policy.

The development of technical terms under the influence of social factors and their formation as a system is explained by the theory of terminological systems of linguists⁷. Superansky emphasizes that the change in technical terms depends on technological progress and the needs of society⁸. The global expansion of English aviation terms (autopilot, flight deck, wake turbulence) and the emergence of terms in Russian appropriate to new technologies (беспилотник, самопиसेц) are based on socio-technical factors.

There are several views of scholars on the formation of aviation terms as transnational units in the global communication system, including Anderson and Schjoldager, who emphasize that technical terms create an international discourse field⁹. Therefore, English aviation terms such as crosswind component, overspeed, runway incursion are used in the same sense throughout the world, while in Russian they come directly from English sources (кроссвинд, овэрспид, etc.). This process forms the global sociolinguistic dynamics of aviation language.

According to the sociolinguistic analysis of the professional discourse context of aviation terms, "a team of specialists should have its own special terminological repertoire"¹⁰. Pilots, dispatchers, and technicians constitute such a professional community. The use of English terms such as roger, negative contact, hold visual, and Russian terms such as разработаю, занимайте исполнительный старт, вижу полосу in their speech indicates that aviation

⁴ Trudgill P. The Social Differentiation of English in Norwich. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 1974 – P. 79.

⁵ Trudgill P. Sociolinguistics: An Introduction to Language and Society. London: Penguin Books. 1995. – P. 87.

⁶ Spolsky B. Language Policy. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 2004. – P. 76.

⁷ Суперанская А.В., Подольская Н.В., Васильева Н.В. Терминологический словарь. Москва: Наука. 1989.

⁸ Суперанская А. В. Общая терминология: Вопросы теории. Москва: Наука. 1976. – P. 178.

⁹ Andersen H.; Schjoldager A. Terminology in Global Contexts. Copenhagen: Copenhagen Business School Press. 2010. – P. 26.

¹⁰ Swales J.M. Genre Analysis: English in Academic and Research Settings. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 1990. – P. 112.

terminology changes and develops under the influence of the internal communicative needs of a particular professional community.

English is the dominant language in aviation, not only as a technical, but also as a means of social, professional and international communication. This terminology is used as a single standard among the professional community around the world - pilots, dispatchers, engineers and security personnel. English terms are used in a uniform, unchanging form on international air routes, which reduces misunderstandings in communication and increases safety.

The results of the analysis show that English aviation terms are used as a single standard in the professional community. For example, in ATC communication between pilots and dispatchers:

Cleared to land - permission to land is granted;

Go-around - abort maneuver before landing;

Line up and wait - orientation to the runway and waiting for permission.

For example, on international flights, a Japanese pilot pronounces the phrase "approach" with a Japanese accent, but the dispatcher understands it. In this way, English acts as a single standard within the professional community.

According to sociolinguistic stratification related to age and experience, professional groups and young professionals use English aviation terms differently:

Young pilots and new professionals use more abbreviations and global terms. For example:

FMS (Flight Management System)

TCAS (Traffic Collision Avoidance System)

VOR (VHF Omnidirectional Range)

Experienced professionals sometimes use local or Russian terms: such as взлёт, посадка (landing and takeoff) шасси (landing gear).

In Russia and Uzbekistan, air traffic control and safety terms: Mayday, Pan-Pan, Runway incursion are used in English. Technical terms are sometimes translated into the local language: hydraulic system, chassis, etc.

Although there are local translations in documents and educational materials today, it is observed that English terms prevail in practical communication.

English terms dominate in international communication, while local translations are used more in academic or educational contexts. This situation demonstrates linguistic code-switching and adaptation to global communication. The significance of each term in flight safety, emergency situations, and international air traffic control communication is analyzed. This sociolinguistically reveals the socio-cultural and professional function of the terms.

Russian aviation terminology has historically been formed as a unique, independent system. The terms developed during the Soviet era were not only technically accurate, but also corresponded to the normative features of professional culture and the national language. For example, terms such as take-off (flight before landing), landing (landing), flight attendant (flight attendant), and steering wheel (control element) were once accepted by the professional community as a single and clear concept. However, in the current era, in the context of globalization and international aviation standards, English terms are actively

entering the Russian aviation lexicon. For example, terms such as runway (писта), briefing (инструктаж), flight level (уровень полёта), and holding point (точка ожидания) are increasingly used in practical communication. This process demonstrates the adaptation of the Russian language to global communication and the sociolinguistic dynamics.

Accent and pronunciation are also sociolinguistically important in international communication. Pilots and dispatchers use English terms in accordance with ICAO pronunciation standards, which is of great importance in terms of integration and safety of the language in the international community.

We can observe that the use of terms in Russian aviation terminology is directly related to professional groups, age and level of experience. This differentiation demonstrates the sociolinguistic stratification of the language and is important in understanding communication within the professional community.

In Russian aviation terminology, the translation of terms and their adaptation to the national language have undergone dramatic changes in recent years. This process is important not only in technical terms, but also in socio-cultural and sociolinguistic contexts. In fact, the translation of terms into the national language and their use alongside English terms is closely related to global integration, communication safety and professional culture.

As an example, let's take the term ILS (Instrument Landing System). Previously, in the Russian version, this system was called pribornaya posadka. This term is completely Russian and based on technical description, meaning the landing of an aircraft using instruments. However, in recent years, in the process of adapting to international aviation standards and ICAO requirements, the abbreviation ILS is often used unchanged in Russian. Thus, the translation of the term into the national language is gradually changing to the form of an abbreviation, but the meaning and practical function are preserved. This process is an example of socio-cultural adaptation: Russian aviation terms are quickly adapting to the requirements of global communication, but the technical description of the local language is also preserved.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the social dynamics of aviation terminology in English and Russian clearly demonstrates the process of adaptation of the professional layers of the language in the field to international standards and the requirements of global communication. As a result of the global dominance of English, many terms are used unchanged and play a dominant role in other languages, which ensures the uniform understanding of terms in international communication. At the same time, although terminology in Russian was formed as an independent system during the Soviet era, English terms and abbreviations are now actively introduced, which reflects the adaptation of the Russian aviation lexicon to global requirements. Sociolinguistic stratification is manifested in the way each professional group uses terms, that is, pilots prefer operational terms, dispatchers prefer standard phraseological expressions, engineers prefer technical terms, young specialists use English abbreviations more often, while older specialists use local or Soviet-era terms. The process of translation and adaptation of terms to the national language also demonstrates the adaptation to global standards and socio-cultural context. Also, changes in accent, pronunciation and normative pressure in international communication serve to ensure safety and guarantee effective communication. In general, the social dynamics of

aviation terms in English and Russian allow for a deep analysis of the adaptation of language to global integration, sociolinguistic differentiation between professional strata, and socio-cultural behavior of the professional community, which serves to increase the efficiency and safety of aviation communication.

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